

Term	Paper Number	References
Tacit and Explicit	P5	These are the staffs that utilize the risk data for risk mitigation process (tacit knowledge). The risk data from the experts are generated as risk report and use as support for performing treating the risk.
	P6	*KM practices and techniques provide several options to be used by the organization to capture tacit and explicit knowledge and share it throughout the KM processes. *KBRC focuses on capturing both the explicit and tacit knowledge exist within people and artifacts inside and outside the organization (Becerra-Fernandez et al., 2004).
	P7	*It captures both explicit and tacit knowledge in documents. *The experts use the client tier to codify tacit knowledge, while the management and staffs use the client tier to utilize explicit codified knowledge to mitigate risk in ICT.
Internal and External	P3	Project Management encompasses as many as five primary areas including: external and internal environments of the project;
	P5	Risk mitigation is performed by Internal IT personnel in teams.
	P6	Knowledge sharing is executed by disseminating and exploiting the captured or discovered knowledge from the organization whether the source is internal or external (Sun & Gang, 2006).
	P7	The knowledge warehouse is collation of information captured from ICT know-how, lessons learnt, in-depth internal expertise, case studies, internal and external case-based knowledge, best practices external benchmarking and engineering standards.
Risk repository	P5	* Each of the components is linked to the knowledge base which serves as the risk repository to record and update risks, and make reports by compiling those risk records. * Most of the existing models do not make use of risk repository such as knowledgebase.
	P6	KBRR (Knowledge-Based Risk Repository)
	P7	The access to such knowledge means that the risk repository is capable of enabling the use of past successes and failures captured to mitigate risks in ICT.
Knowledge Capture	P6	It also portrays knowledge essentials as components that contain the foundation for utilizing knowledge and the practices and techniques options used to employ, capture and share knowledge throughout KM processes.
	P7	Knowledge Capture: This is the phase where the risk knowledge is produced. The tacit knowledge is collected from the experts in the organization.
Knowledge codification	P7	Knowledge codification involves the transformation of knowledge into information, thus codification is a process of creation of messages, expressing pre-existing knowledge, which can then be processed as information [20].
Share knowledge	P6	It also portrays knowledge essentials as components that contain the foundation for utilizing knowledge and the practices and techniques options used to employ, capture and share knowledge throughout KM processes.
	P7	Share Knowledge: Involves the dissemination and distribution of explicit knowledge in order to support practitioners in mitigating risk in ICT.

Knowledge application	P6	Knowledge application: provides a portal to access the latest information on the KBRR and updates to knowledge relevant to risks residing in the repository.
	P7	This layer also updates and edits the knowledge by removing the outdated knowledge and collecting the feedbacks of practitioners and decision maker about the application of knowledge in their decisions to mitigate risk.
Embed Knowledge	P7	Embed Knowledge: Risk mitigation strategies, actions and methods require are codified, organized and represented as risk knowledge in the enterprise knowledgebase. This includes the activities of preserve, maintain and index risk knowledge.
Strutured	P2	We collected empirical data through several sessions of iterative and structured interviews over 12 months across two medium-size software companies.
	P3	The risk identification stage develops through qualitative methods such as structured questionnaire and expert judgment, which allows determination of the risks that could appear during the project and impact its performances.
Unstructured	P3	These key descriptors are described thanks to the use of templates composed of closed and unstrutued questions.
Risk mitigation	P1	The first primary step of risk management is risk prioritization and it involves risk identification, risk analysis and risk prioritization (risk evaluation and risk mitigation)
	P3	Executing Process: This third process is composed of two interconnected phases with the main objective to provide the risk mitigation plan: conceive risk actions and plan deployment.
	P5	The need for adequate data in the risk mitigation process to provide support to practitioners.
	P6	This way, the manager learns from the facts of former projects, avoiding the recurrence of problems and reusing actions, which were previously successful in the risk mitigation or contingency (Farias, Travassos, & Rocha, 2003).
Risk identification	P1	These software risk management includes risk identification, risk measurement and evaluation, risk reduction or elimination, risk reporting and risk transfer (Zhang et al., 2015).
	P3	The risk identification stage develops through qualitative methods such as structured questionnaire and expert judgment, which allows determination of the risks that could appear during the project and impact its performances.
	P5	In risk identification component potential risks are determined by Risk analysts, IT Manager, Project team, System Analyst Senior Engineer by using process such as Risk Rating, Screening, Examination of risk drivers and assumption risk analysis.
Risk treatment	P5	Risk treatment is defining an effective strategy to solve the risks associated with the various risk classes defined.
	P6	Where possible, events, hazards, threats, or situations that can create risks should be identified to aid future risk treatment (“Systems and software engineering – Life cycle processes – Risk management,” 2006).

Risk control	P6	During the execution process risk control might require altering the current execution plan, ending the risk or even initiating a contingency plan if the current plan is found to be ineffective and requires starting from the beginning of the risk process if a new risk has been identified (Perera & Holsomback, 2005).
	P1	The other step of risk management is risk control and it involves risk management planning, risk resolution, and risk monitoring.
	P3	The Risk Control sub process is dedicated to design and specify control strategies (risk avoidance, risk sharing, risk reduction and risk transfer) in order to monitor plan deployment and to capitalize experiences.
	P6	Also, this process will evaluate the risk execution progress and risk control mechanisms continuously.